

Case Report

**A Rare Case of Malignant Otitis Externa Complicated by
Occipital Bone Osteomyelitis**

Dr.Sofia Ahmed AlKhatibi AlFalasi , MBBS *¹, Dr.Ali Al-Fraihat - MB BCh BAO²· Prof.Jamal
Kassouma – MD,FRCS Ed, FRCS orl-hns , ENT Consultant³

1,2,3. Dubai health , otolaryngology department - Dubai hospital.

***Correspondence to:** Dr. Sofia Ahmed AlKhatibi AlFalasi, MBBS, otolaryngology department - Dubai Hospital.

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Received: 06 April 2024

Published: 01 May 2024

Introduction

A 65-year-old male with a known case of diabetes mellitus, hypertension, dyslipidemia, and multiple comorbidities and a smoker presented to the ENT clinic, with a 1-year history of recurrent right ear discharge and ear pain. He developed right otitis externa, which progressed into right-sided malignant otitis externa, initially affecting osteomastoiditis and further complicated by severe osteomyelitis involving the occipital bone.

During the first visit, an otologic examination revealed ear congestion, ear discharge, decreased hearing in bilateral ears, and ear tenderness with edema on the right ear. Regarding his hearing, he has mentioned that it has been reduced since his childhood, so it is not new to him.

Initially, he was treated with Ciprofloxacin 250mg tablet, Ciprofloxacin-hydrocortisone otic solution with pain medication Ibuprofen and Paracetamol. It was suggested that he take all his medications as prescribed.

The patient experienced discomfort, congestion, inflammation, and granulation tissue in his right ear, but with no discharge. He was advised to be hospitalized but declined. He took prescribed medications, including the new antibiotic Levofloxacin. Later, he returned with significant discomfort and impaired hearing. He was advised to be admitted for intravenous therapy, but has declined.

He was later hospitalized after failing to improve on outpatient medications. Analgesics and intravenous ceftazidime 1000 mg for every 12 hours were administered during admission instead of ciprofloxacin due to him having kidney failure & according to swab culture.

The first CT petrous bone scan of the right side of the ear revealed complete opacification, indicating chronic otitis media and otitis externa, along with right-side chronic mastoiditis. After 1 month of treatment, the patient started to improve & he was discharged after two months.

A microbiological culture of the infected right ear revealed the presence of *Escherichia coli*, necessitating a repeat CT scan. Which revealed aggressive infective/inflammatory processes in the right external auditory canal (malignant otitis externa) with extension and involvement of the middle ear (otomastoiditis) and erosive changes in the right area of the petrous bone.

A pure tone audiometry test revealed severe to profound mixed hearing loss in the right ear and mild to profound sensorineural hearing loss in the left ear.

Later a third CT scan was performed due to continued ear discomfort and as a follow-up from the previous CT scan. In comparison to the previous CT scan done, no significant interval changes were shown; however, left mastoiditis was developed. He was going to undergo another ear exploration surgery with bone debridement; however, it was canceled as he was unfit for anesthesia due to him having severe hypertension which was 210/40 mmhg and taking two anticoagulants & having multiple co-morbidities.

Image 1 - CT Scan, Petrous Bone, Coronal View

Image 2 - CT Scan -Petrous Bone, Axial View

Discussion

Malignant otitis externa is the osteomyelitis of the temporal bone that usually occurs in elderly diabetic or otherwise immunocompromised patients; occasionally, the infection can spread and cause a skull base osteomyelitis. In particular, microangiopathy and impaired blood circulation in patients with diabetes may play a main role in the pathogenesis of the disease. Other causes can favor vascular impairment, such as radiotherapy or an unhealthy diet[1]. The condition is linked to serious side effects, including cranial nerve involvement, as well as a high morbidity and mortality rate[1]. MOE has also been shown in immunocompromised or diabetic children; however, the prevalence is lower than in elderly patients with diabetes[1].

Symptoms of malignant otitis externa encompass intense ear pain, discharge from the ear, a sense of ear fullness, and diminished hearing[2]. If the infection extends, it may lead to jaw discomfort (TMJ joint pain), hemi-facial pain, headaches, and trismus[1]. Facial nerve palsy can also occur in some cases[1]. The Levenson criteria may be used for diagnosis, which involve factors like persistent otitis externa, severe nocturnal otalgia, purulent otorrhea, granulation tissue in the external auditory canal, the presence of *Pseudomonas* bacteria in ear culture, and underlying conditions like diabetes or immunocompromised patients[2]. All of these clinical features may aid in making a diagnosis for MOE[2].

The most common microbiological agent for MOE is *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Other bacteria in MOE include *Staphylococcus aureus*, *S. epidermidis*, *Proteus mirabilis*, *Klebsiella oxytoca*, and *P. cepacia*[1]. In addition, a mycotic superinfection can exacerbate the condition. The most common fungal organism causing MOE is *Aspergillus fumigatus*[1]. A bacterial culture provides a base for antibiotic selection. Ciprofloxacin (with or without rifampin), new-generation fluoroquinolones, or third-generation cephalosporin are often used if culture findings are negative[2].

Fungal organisms or a combination of bacterial and fungal infections cause MOE; therefore, doctors recommend antifungal medication[1]. When patients report complications such as facial palsy or temporomandibular joint discomfort, an imaging scan is required[1]. To assess the occurrence of bony erosion, a high-resolution CT scan of the temporal bone is typically employed[3]. Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) provides higher resolution for evaluating soft tissue, particularly the parotid gland, meninges, and cranial nerves[4]. When compared to typical MRI sequences, diffusion-weighted MRI gives greater anatomical resolution[1]. However, combining CT and MRI allows for more sensitive diagnostic imaging, and diffusion-weighted MRI assists in assessing disease progression[2]. Complications of

malignant otitis externa and osteomyelitis include meningitis, abscess, sagittal, dural, and cavernous sinus thrombosis[1].

Just like most of the clinical symptoms and features of MOE, the patient in this report was diabetic and immunocompromised with several co-morbidities. What was different in this case was that the pathogen from his ear culture was not from the most common organism that causes MOE (*Pseudomonas aeruginosa*); it was *Escherichia coli*, which makes this case more unique. *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*) is not commonly associated with malignant otitis externa (MOE).

MOE is a severe and potentially life-threatening infection of the external ear canal and surrounding structures, typically seen in elderly individuals with underlying conditions such as diabetes or immunocompromised systems. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, a bacterium found in soil, water, and damp environments, typically causes the infection. It is often linked to MOE, causing infections in wounds and the ear. The presence of *Escherichia coli* in the ear is unusual, suggesting a more severe or secondary infection. However, the primary pathogen associated with MOE is usually *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*.

Our patient had a 1-year history of recurrent right ear discharge and ear pain. His condition began as right otitis externa, which has developed into right-sided malignant otitis externa that initially involved osteomastoiditis and was complicated by severe osteomyelitis involving the occipital bone. He was treated exclusively with antibiotics while being hospitalized, analgesics with ear solutions, and underwent one ear exploration surgery. He was supposed to undergo ear exploration again with bone debridement after a few months; however, he was not fit for surgery & anesthesia due to him taking anticoagulants & due to his health conditions.

In our case, there was a marked progression of right MOE that has developed into osteomyelitis of the occipital bone. In the CT petrous bone scan, persistent abnormal soft tissue has been shown involving the outer and inner right ear, with erosive changes of the tegmen tympani ossicles, scutum, middle ear cavity walls, and mastoid portion of the right temporal bone. Also, irregularity of the facial nerve canal has been seen along the labyrinthine and tympanic segments of the facial nerve due to erosion or inflammation, and diffuse opacification of the right mastoid air cells was also seen.

Searching the literature, there has only been one case reported with MOE that has progressed to osteomyelitis of the occipital bone. However, the difference in the case is that it was caused by *Corynebacterium Amycolatum*, whereas in our case is that the pathogen from his ear culture was

Escherichia coli. The typical cause of this disease is that it spreads to the skull base, affecting the lower fourth cranial nerve, and occasionally progresses to the other side of the skull base, but in our case it did not go to the skull base and instead it went posteriorly into the occipital bone, making it rare.

The presence of *Escherichia coli* in the ear is unusual, suggesting a more severe or secondary infection. The CT petrous bone, revealed aggressive infective and inflammatory processes in the right external auditory canal which caused malignant otitis externa with extension into the middle ear which caused osteomyelitis of the occipital bone.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the case of malignant otitis externa (MOE) in a diabetic and immunocompromised patient with multiple co-morbidities is unique due to the presence of *Escherichia coli*, an uncommon pathogen for MOE. The patient's 1-year history of recurrent ear issues, progressing from otitis externa to severe MOE involving the mastoid causing osteomyelitis and extending to the occipital bone, emphasizes the seriousness of the illness.

The standard treatment is hospitalization, antibiotic therapy, analgesics, and an ear exploration surgery. He was going to undergo another ear exploration surgery with bone debridement on right ear; however, it was canceled as he was unfit for anesthesia due to him having severe hypertension which was 210/40 mmhg and taking 2 anticoagulants & having multiple co-morbidities.

References

1. Bruschini, L., Berrettini, S., Christina, C., Ferranti, S., Fabiani, S., Cavezza, M., Forli, F., Santoro, A., & Tagliaferri, E. (2019). Extensive Skull Base Osteomyelitis Secondary to Malignant Otitis Externa. *The journal of international advanced otology*, 15(3), 463–465.
2. Carlton DA, Perez EE, Smouha EE. Malignant external otitis: The shifting treatment paradigm. *Am J Otolaryngol* 2018; 39: 41-5.
3. Rubin J, Yu VL. Malignant external otitis: insights into pathogenesis, clinical manifestations, diagnosis, and therapy. *Am J Med* 1988; 85: 391- 8.

4. Eguchi T, Basugi A, Kanai I, Miyata Y, Nasuno T, Hamada Y. Malignant external otitis following radiotherapy for oral cancer: A case report. *Medicine (Baltimore)*. 2018; 97: e10898.

